

Experimental Study on Coffee Management System for North-Eastern Region, India

Silvia Narzary¹ and Bhaskar Saha²

^{1,2}*Department of Multimedia Communication Design, Central Institute of Technology, Kokrajhar.*

Abstract: This topic of study describes the design and development of a mobile application to assist coffee farmers in the Northeast region in tracking their coffee plants, managing the harvest process, and increasing overall output. The primary goal of the application is to reduce waste in coffee plantations by providing farmers with valuable knowledge and insights into coffee plantation management. The application aims to empower farmers and improve the efficiency and productivity of coffee farming in the Northeast by incorporating features such as plant tracking, harvest management, and comprehensive information on pre-harvest and post-harvest care.

Practical Implications: The findings of the study provide practical insights into reducing coffee waste by equipping farmers in Northeast India with valuable knowledge and insights into coffee plantation management from digital technology. The study adopts an experimental approach to designing a mobile application that helps farmers track their coffee plants, streamline the harvest process, and enhance overall productivity.

Keywords: Coffee plantation; Northeast; Reduce waste; Sustain

1. Introduction

Coffee is a worldwide commodity-based and foreign exchange earner, and is economically significant, even in India. However, due to deregulation, evolving corporate strategies, and shifting consumption patterns, the coffee industry has undergone transformative changes in recent decades. Maintaining coffee production, minimizing waste, and providing farmers with access to education and digital techniques are critical goals in Northeast India. The purpose of this introduction is to emphasize the importance of sustainable coffee practices, reducing waste, and empowering farmers in Northeast India to increase production through digital techniques and education.

Providing proper education and training to coffee farmers in the region is crucial. By imparting knowledge on modern farming techniques, sustainable practices, and value-added processes, farmers can upscale their production and improve the quality of their coffee beans. Empowering farmers with this knowledge not only increase their income potential but also contributes to the overall growth and development of the coffee industry in Northeast India.

Besides, the focus on sustainability standards, ecosystem preservation, and cultivation practices on coffee plant has gained importance. To ensure long-term sustainability, it is crucial to integrate digital techniques into coffee farming. Digital platforms offer real-time information on best practices, weather patterns, pest control, and market trends, enabling farmers to make informed decisions, optimize resources, and enhance productivity.

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The purpose of this study, is to examine the current state of coffee production in the region, investigate the potential of sustainability standards and propose a design system for coffee management system to facilitate the growth of coffee industry farmers to thrive the coffee industry in northeast where waste can be reduced, and production can be optimized.

1.1. Coffee Plantation in India

Coffee production in India is primarily concentrated in the hilly regions of South Indian states. Karnataka holds the dominant position, accounting for 71% of India's coffee production, with a significant contribution from Kodagu alone, which produces 33% of the country's coffee. Kerala follows with a share of 21%, while Tamil Nadu contributes 5% to the overall production, equivalent to approximately 8,200 tones as shown in **Figure 1**. Renowned for its exceptional quality, Indian coffee is predominantly grown under shade, distinguishing it from coffee produced in direct sunlight across the globe. (Coffee Board, 2023)

Figure 1: Coffee Production in India.

Source : <https://www.mapsofindia.com/answers/states/which-indian-state-is-the-largest-producer-of-coffee/>

The country has many coffee growers, estimated at around 250,000, with the vast majority (98%) being small-scale growers (Anupindi & Sivakumar, 2007). Despite its significant presence in coffee cultivation, India's global contribution remains relatively modest, accounting for only 4.5% of global coffee production in 2005 (Illy & Viani, 2005). Notably, nearly 80% of Indian coffee is exported to countries such as Germany, Russia, Spain, Belgium, Slovenia, the United States, the United Kingdom, Japan, Greece, the Netherlands, and France. Italy is the leading importer, accounting for 29% of total exports. The Suez Canal is an important shipping route for a large portion of India's coffee exports.

Coffee cultivation in India dates back to the 17th century, when Baba Budan introduced it to the Chikmagalur hills in present-day Karnataka. India is now the world's sixth-largest coffee producer. Coffee is primarily grown in the southern states of Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, and Andhra Pradesh, as well as parts of the Northeast (Coffee production in India, 2023). All coffee grown in India is grown in the shade, usually in two tiers. Coffees that are inter-cropped with spices like cardamom, cinnamon, clove, and nutmeg gain aromatics from the inter-cropping, storage, and handling functions (Davids,

2001) Coffee growing in India is grouped in 3 categories, such as the Traditional areas representing, southern states. The non-traditional areas representing Eastern Ghats of the Country and the North-eastern region of India as show in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Coffee growing Region.

Source : <https://www.indiacoffee.org/coffee-regions-india.html>

1.2. Coffee Plantation in Northeast India

Coffee cultivation in the NE Region began in 1953 in the Cachar District of Assam. Commercial agriculture began in the 1970s at Garo Hills (Meghalaya) in order to wean the local community away from Jhum cultivation practices. (Rau, 2007)

Coffee is grown on 479 hectares in Arunachal Pradesh, 429 hectares in Assam, 1,100 hectares in Meghalaya, 1,300 hectares in Mizoram, 932 hectares in Nagaland, and 264 hectares in Tripura, according to data. Northeast produce both Robusta and Arabica. In Assam itself there is 3 regions where coffee is grown. It is cultivated majorly in Halflong in Dima haso district, mostly arabica beans.

Robusta coffee is primarily grown in the Assam districts of Karbi Anglong, Chirang, and Bijni, among others. Karbi Anglong also has a coffee research center. Arabica and Robusta are the two most common coffee varieties. Robusta is grown at lower elevations (500-1000 meters above sea level), whereas Arabica is grown at higher elevations (1000-1500 meters above sea level) (Bora, 2023).

1.3. Highest Production

Karnataka is India's leading coffee producer, with a total production volume of 2.33 lakh metric tons. Karnataka is the leading coffee producer in India, with the most coffee plantations. The state produces 70% of India's coffee. Furthermore, the state's total annual coffee production in India was calculated to be 2.33 lakh metric tons in fiscal year 2022. Kodagu district accounts for 44% of Karnataka's total coffee area. Furthermore, its annual production was calculated to be 1,06,921/ha. The coffee farms in this district are owned by small farmers. (Top 10 Coffee Producing States in India – Annual Production, 2023) Followed by Kerala being the 2nd largest production of Coffee producing 67700 metric tons annual production. Tamil Nadu being the Third largest production with 17,875 metric tons annual year. Andhra Pradesh occupies the fourth position as it produces 7,425 metric tons of coffee annual year. Odisha is the fifth largest coffee producer, producing 550 metric tons per year. Tripura is the sixth largest producer of coffee in India with 12 to 14 metric tons of production.

1.4 Types of Coffee Bean

India grows two types of coffee beans: Arabica and Robusta. Arabica beans are known for their delicate flavour, acidity, and aroma, whereas Robusta beans are known for their robust and full-bodied flavour. These distinct varieties are grown in different parts of India. Arabica is primarily grown in the elevated areas of the Western Ghats, whereas Robusta is grown throughout the country.

2. Primary Study

Primary Study was done in two phase, 1st it was conducted through online survey to get a general idea about the knowledge of the regional presence of coffee in the area.

Figure 3. Survey Questions.

Survey Findings (Figure 3)

- 71.4% wants to promote coffee produced from Northeast if given a chance.
- 42.9% believes that due to no knowledge, NER lacks to produce coffee despite situation weather , soil conditions.
- It was also seen that 71% are actually aware of coffee being produced in Northeast.
- 28.6 % think that due to no labor support, lack of digital system, no knowledge and No government support Northeast region is lacking to produce coffee despite the suitable conditions.

2.1. Survey - 2

A survey was conducted in Shillong, Mawrynkan village to get some insights of the coffee production. Questions Related to their management, Type of bean harvested, pain care etc.

It was observed that they mostly grow Both robustica and Arabica coffee, in this Survey it was known that there are many challenges in its managements due to lack of knowledge and due loss of crop due to rain as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Shillong coffee cultivation

3. Research Gap

One of the major research gaps in the field of coffee production and management is the lack of an effective management system. Coffee plants are being wasted due to inadequate care and premature management practises, resulting in a decrease in overall production. To address the issue, the aim here is to conduct an experimental study on coffee management systems for India's North-east region is being conducted.

This experiments objective is to develop an intuitive and user-friendly mobile application interface that will allow coffee farmers to easily navigate and use the system, allowing coffee farmers to monitor the growth and health of the plant and input appropriate data to receive service assistance. Furthermore, the research will focus on integrating vendor profiles and trader profiles within the system, creating an ecosystem that connects farmers with necessary resources and market opportunities. This integration aims to establish a seamless flow of information and transactions between coffee growers, vendors, and traders, fostering a collaborative and sustainable coffee industry.

4. Design Process

Research

Analysis

Ideate

Prototype

Testing

4.1. Research Methodology

A total of 20 participants were taken out of which there were coffee land owners and growers within the age of 25 to 50 years old, and as we communicated with the growers, a few pain points were listed after that as shown in Figure 5.

“ There is Lack of Knowledge on coffee Cultivation Techniques”

“ lacks expertise in leveraging digital technology”

“ Had to find right vendors and tools when needed”

Figure 5. Pain point analysis.

4.2. SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- A digital platform for coffee farmers to manage their plantations, track crop health, access real-time information, and receive personalized recommendations would streamline their daily operations and decision-making process, saving time and effort.
- A coffee management system would suggest guidance on best practices, pest control measures, post-harvest care, and market trends, empowering farmers with the necessary knowledge to improve their coffee production.
- By collecting and analyzing data on coffee plantations, weather patterns, and market trends, the application generates valuable insights. Coffee farmers can leverage this information to make informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and enhance their overall productivity.

Weakness

- Due to limited access to technology, internet connectivity, or digital literacy, some coffee farmers may face difficulties in adopting and effectively utilizing the application. To ensure widespread adoption, efforts should be made to provide training and support.
- There is a lack of awareness regarding the implementation of smart digital techniques in coffee cultivation.

Opportunity

- It would cater the needs of environmentally conscious consumers and coffee industry stakeholders.
- Digitalization and data storing of crop details during the process of Harvest.

Threats

- In regions with limited internet connectivity or inadequate digital infrastructure, the application's usability and effectiveness may be compromised.

4.3. Current system flow

The current system flow depicts the direct link between coffee farmers and corporations, as well as government policies and small-scale traders. These corporations then engage with larger traders and end users on a large scale, frequently involving multiple companies or factories as illustrated in [Figure 6](#). Thus, Individual growth opportunities for coffee farmers are reduced because of this chain.

Current System Flow

Figure 6. Current system flow.

4.4. Approached system flow

This approach demonstrated in Figure 7, shows how coffee growers would operate within the system. By integrating system data input throughout the cultivation process, growers can actively participate and monitor each step. This enables them to easily detect any abnormalities and promptly diagnose potential issues. This proactive approach minimizes the likelihood of waste occurring at a later stage, ensuring efficient and productive coffee cultivation.

Approached System Flow for Coffee Grower

Figure 7. Approached System Flow for Growers.

4.5. Concept Development

To establish a healthy and sustainable ecosystem within the coffee management system, it was observed that the inclusion of local vendors and traders is crucial. This concept development in Figure 8 integrates and enables access to valuable market information, facilitates equipment procurement for farmers, and establishes connections with traders. By fostering this ecosystem, trust is built, and coffee growers can expand their production and efficiently manage their businesses with this method. The interface of the designed mobile app is presented in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 8. Concept of the system.

Figure 9. Wireframe.

Figure 10. Final Outcome.

5. Screen Walk through

The login screen (Figure 11) provides users with the option to choose between being a grower, trader, or vendor, regardless of their choice, they will be directed to the main screen. On the main screen, users are prompted to provide additional information to set up their respective profiles on the subsequent screen. In addition to the search bar, an audio recognition button is implemented to minimize the need for text input by users as seen in Figure 12.

Figure 11. Log in.

Figure 12. Set your profile.

Figure 13. Crop care.

Figure 14. Market

After setting up their profile, the user is directed to the home page, as illustrated in Figure 13. This screen displays the grower's profile, where they have the option to choose between crop care and market as shown in Figure 14. Within each section, there is also an option for expert assistance, allowing growers to seek help during the cultivation process if needed.

Under the crop care section, the crop calculator provides estimated stages of crop cultivation based on user input. The pest control option allows users to seek assistance with pest management or diagnose plant issues before further damage occurs. The videos section provides access to multiple videos relevant to the grower's requirements. The crop calendar keeps track of the data input regarding the crop's progress as shown in Figure 15.

The equipment section, depicted in Figure 14, allows growers to easily search for tools and items needed during the cultivation process. Furthermore, the vendor section makes it simple to sell and find saplings for coffee growers.

Figure 15. Crop Calendar

Figure 16. Upload photo

The **Figure 15** includes a crop calendar section. When the user clicks on it, they are taken to a screen, as shown in **Figure 16**, where they can select the plant's stage and enter data. The appropriate harvest period for the plant is then suggested and tracked by an analyzer. After submitting the stage of development, the user is taken to a screen where they can confirm the process. The user is asked to upload a picture or video of the plant stage to help with verification as shown in **Figure 16**. This step allows the user to begin crop care and displays the estimated harvest time in the calendar, as shown in **Figure 17**.

Figure 17. Crop calculator.

Figure 18. Your products

Figure 19. Reports.

When registering as a vendor, the user is given the option of listing their products in the "Your Product" section, as illustrated in **Figure 18**. In addition, the "Report" section, as shown in **Figure 19**, provides the user with a business analysis. This analysis contains specific details about the user's earnings, orders, product tracking, out-of-stock items, and sales. It allows local vendors to keep a digital record of their data and provides them with an illustrated overview of their business performance.

Figure 20. Sales.

Figure 20 depicts a visual representation of how users can view, track, and analyze their sales. This section is useful for vendors because it allows them to keep organized records of their business activities. It allows the vendor to track sales data in a structured and systematic manner, allowing for better analysis and insights into their business performance.

5.1. Design Observations

The design approach was to use visually appealing icons with color code as show in **Figure 21**, allowing for enhanced understanding and visualization of information. Additionally, color coding is employed to aid in pattern recognition, making it easier for users to remember and interpret data. These design elements contribute to a more intuitive and visually engaging user experience within the system.

Figure 21. Design Observation.

Figure 22. Interaction with Coffee owners and coffee growers of North-east India.

6. Validation

Survey Question –

1. Can you recognize the pictures?
2. Can you tell which stage of the coffee plant it belongs to?
3. Is it simple to input data?

6.1. Interpretation

These are some of the concerns -

- Text should be in local language with simple interpretation.
- Application should have both feature (Text as well as Voice)
- Buttons should be more intuitive.
- It will be helpful to contact people with similar problems.

7. Discussion and Conclusion

In conclusion, the coffee plantation management application aims to empower Northeast farmers by providing them with an intuitive tool to track their coffee plants, manage the harvest process efficiently, and gain knowledge on best practices, in a way that the system also supports the other local vendors and traders in the current ecosystem. By addressing the challenges faced by coffee farmers in the region, the application has the potential to enhance productivity, reduce wastage, provide them quick solution, and contribute to the overall growth and sustainability of the coffee industry in the Northeast.

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